

Technical Profile Interview Script

Warm Up:

- For how long have you been in the company?
- What is your current Job Position?
- How many people are on your team? What are their job positions?

Context information:

- What is your team responsible for? What are your main responsibilities?
 - For BizDev responsibilities: Who defined these responsibilities?
 - For BizDev responsibilities: Do you think you spend too much time fulfilling these responsibilities?
- Does your team have regular meetings? What are those meetings for? Who participate on them?
 - Do you know if your leader participates on other meetings?

Requirements Handling:

- How do you get the specifications over the features you/your team develop?
- What do you do when you don't understand one requirement, or when you have doubts about priorities?
 - Do you think you spend too much time waiting for clarification?
- Do you know of any projects or features that were proposed/defined by the technology team? Case positive:
 - How frequently does this happen? Does this happen for most features, or only for small features?
 - Where they successful? Why do you think so?
 - Were people from business team involved on these projects? Were they aware of it?
 - What members of the tech team were involved? Were there analysts involved, or only tech leaders?

Communication on the BizDev interface:

- Do you usually need to communicate with people from business teams, such as Product, Content, Growth, Marketing?
 - What teams do you communicate with?
 - What are the reasons for this communication? What is discussed?
 - How frequent is this communication?
 - How do you evaluate this communication? Do you think you understand each other? Do some information tend to be lost on the process?
 - Is the communication efficient? Or is it slow?

- Do you think you need to use technical jargons? If you do, do you think this is a problem for business people?
- Do you think the communication with the business area could be improved?
 - Case positive: How do you think it could be improved?
 - Do you take any effort to improve this communication? Case positive, do you receive any help for this?
 - Have you perceived any effort taken by business teams to improve this communication? Any effort taken by the company?

Relationship with business sector:

- Have you noticed conflicts between business and technology areas?
 - What were the reasons of these conflicts?
 - What were the consequences?
 - Do you think these conflicts can still happen?
- Do you trust the decisions taken by business teams? Why?
 - Do business teams usually trust decisions taken by your team? Why?
- Have you perceived any type of action taken in order to improve the relationship between business and development areas? Case positive:
 - What was this action? Which team was responsible for it?
 - How do you compare this relationship before and after these actions?
- How do you perceive your impact on business decisions?

Business and Tech Knowledge:

- How do you evaluate your business knowledge?
- Do people from business area usually take time to share business knowledge with you and your team?
 - Case positive: How does this happen? How frequent is that? Who was behind the decision of sharing this knowledge?
- Do you or your team usually take time to share technology knowledge with business people?
 - Case positive: How does this happen? How frequent is that? Who was behind the decision of sharing this knowledge?

Reactive Points:

When interviewee describes any practice inserted on the BizDev Interface:

- Who defined this practice? What was the motivation behind it?
 - Do you think this practice matches a behavior described on the company's values?
- How frequent is this practice?
 - Do you think you spend too much time performing these practices?

When interviewee talks specifically about technology team performing practices directly linked to business (eg: definition/prioritization of requirements, performance analysis):

- Do analysts also take part on these activities?
- Is the business team receptive to these practices?

When the interviewee talks about the project created on PlayKids App in order to improve general process and communication:

- Do you think that project was necessary? Why?
- What was your participation on that project? How did it affect your work?
- Have you perceived significant changes brought by this project? What changed in terms of:
 - Communication between Business and Technology teams
 - Product quality
 - Overall performance and fulfillment of deadlines